

Acute appendicitis: accuracy of Alvarado Score in the diagnosis

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Abstract: Acute appendicitis causes acute abdomen in surgical patients. The Alvarado score (AS) is used to diagnose acute appendicitis. This study comprised 180 patients with acute appendicitis. Alvarado scores were determined for patients 12 years and older of both sexes. AS 1-4, 5-6, and 7-10 were the patient groups. AA and non-AA rates were compared using different parameters. We analyzed each patient's signs, symptoms, lab results, surgical procedures, and pathology reports. Histopathology confirmed diagnosis. Diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values were calculated. Data analysis utilized SPSS 16. 180 cases were studied, 72 men (40%) and 108 women (60 %). 129 patients (76.6%) were under 30 years of age. 20 percent of patients with Alvarado score 1-4 had acute appendicitis, 35.29 percent with 5-6, and 96% with 7-10. AS increased negative appendectomy rate. AS was 90% accurate in diagnosing acute appendicitis. This study demonstrated no variation in AS reliability by gender, age, or BMI. Alvarado scoring system helps diagnose acute appendicitis before surgery, especially in resource-limited settings.

Keywords: Alvarado scoring, Appendicitis, Histopathology.

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Introduction

There is a lifetime risk of approximately 7 percent of developing acute appendicitis, making it the most common cause of an acute abdomen that requires surgery [1]. Because the symptoms of appendicitis overlap with those of a number of other conditions, diagnosis can be difficult, particularly in the earlier stages of the condition's presentation [2]. Patients may be appropriately triaged into alternative management strategies, such as providing reassurance, pursuing an alternative diagnosis, or observing the patient in the hospital or admitting the patient. In the event that the patient

is admitted to the hospital, the appropriate imaging may be required before moving forward with the appendectomy [3].

Clinical prediction rules, also known as CPRs, are used to quantify the diagnosis of a target disorder by analyzing the findings of key symptoms, signs, and available diagnostic tests. Because of this, clinical prediction rules (CPRs) have independent diagnostic or prognostic value [4]. They can also extend into the process of clinical decision making if probability estimates are linked to management recommendations, at which point they are referred to as clinical decision rules. CPRs have the potential to lower the rate of diagnostic errors, boost quality, and improve the appropriateness of patient care [4]. Alvarado developed a 10-point clinical scoring system for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in 1986 [5]. This system is also known by its acronym, MANTRELS, and it is based on symptoms, signs, and diagnostic tests that are performed on patients who present with suspected acute appendicitis. Figure 1 shows an example of this scoring system.

Fig.1: Probability of appendicitis by the Alvarado score [5]: risk strata and subsequent clinical management strategy.

Patients who present with abdominal pain can be stratified according to their risk using the Alvarado score, which links the likelihood of appendicitis to recommendations regarding whether the patient should be discharged, observed, or undergo surgical intervention [5]. When the probability of appendicitis is in the intermediate range, further investigations such as ultrasound and computed tomography (CT) scanning are recommended [6]. When appendicitis is suspected to be the underlying cause of an acute abdomen, the Alvarado score may be a useful diagnostic aid because of the time lag, high costs, and variable availability of imaging procedures. This is especially true in countries with limited resources, where imaging is not an option.

The American College of Emergency Physicians published a clinical policy document not too long ago that discusses the benefits of using clinical findings to guide decision making in cases of acute appendicitis [7]. According to what is written under the heading of the Alvarado score, "combining various signs and symptoms into a scoring system may be more useful in predicting the presence or absence of appendicitis." The Alvarado score is the only scoring system that is presented in this document; however, it is not a particularly strong recommendation.

The Alvarado score was developed initially as a diagnostic score more than two decades ago; however, its performance and appropriateness for routine clinical use is still unknown at this time. In order to determine the effectiveness of the Alvarado score, the purpose of this research was to carry out a comprehensive review and meta-analysis of previous validation studies on the subject (diagnostic accuracy or discrimination at two cut-points commonly used for decision making, and calibration of the score).

Research Methodology

This study was carried out in the Surgery Department of the Janaki Medical college Teaching Hospital (JMCTH) in Janakpur Dham, Nepal, between the 1st of July 2020 and the 30th of Jan 2022. This study included 180 patients who were randomly selected from among consecutive patients who were admitted during that time period complaining of pain in the right lower abdomen. Patients of any gender and age 12 years or older who participated in the study were considered for inclusion. Patients who suffered from urological, gynecological, or surgical conditions in addition to appendicitis, and particularly patients who had a mass in the right iliac fossa, as well as patients whose documentation in the case sheets was insufficient, were not permitted to participate in the study. The attending surgeon devised a treatment plan for the patient. Patients were categorized into one of three groups based on their AS scores: those with scores of 1-4 (low risk), 5-6 (moderate risk), and 7-10 (high risk) (high risk).

Appendectomy was performed on patients whose AS score was greater than 6. This information was analyzed and correlated with the operative notes as well as the histopathologic examination of the specimen. In order to evaluate the efficacy of the Alvarado scoring system, several metrics, including the negative appendectomy rate, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, sensitivity, and specificity, were computed. The groups were compared based on factors including age (less than or equal to 30 years), gender (male or female), body mass index (less than or equal to 25), and duration of symptoms (less than or equal to 24 hours). It was recorded how patients were managed, whether they were discharged, monitored, or operated on. Patients who underwent surgery were categorized as having acute appendicitis (AA) or not having acute appendicitis (non-AA) (normal appendix). We looked into whether or not the AS was affected by factors such as age, gender, body mass index (BMI), or the duration of symptoms, as well as the diagnostic accuracy of the AS in identifying AA. In order to perform statistical analysis on the data collected for the

study, the program Statistical Package for the Social Sciences for Windows 16.0 was utilized. A significance level of 0.05 was determined for the P value.

Results

In total, 180 patients participated in the research, with 40 percent of the participants being male (72 patients) and the remaining patients being female (108 patients) (60 percent). Patients were split up into the five different groups that are outlined in Table I.

Table I: Distribution of patients according to alvarado score

Score	Male	%Male	female	%Female	Total	%
1-4	14	7.78%	30	16.67%	44	24.44
5-6	30	16.67%	28	15.56%	58	32.22
7-10	28	15.56%	50	27.78%	78	43.34
Total	72		108		180	(100%)

Table II: Age distribution of patients.

Age group (years)	Frequency	Percentage
13-20	78	43.33%
21-30	51	28.33%
31-40	38	21.11%
41-50	7	3.8%
>51	6	3.43%
Total	180	100%

The mean age was 26.4 years older than 10 years. 44 patients, or 24.44 percent, were given a score in the 1–4 range, 58 patients, or 32.22 percent, were given a score in the 5–6 range, and 78 patients, or 43.34 percent, were given a score in the 7–10 range. Within the group score range of 1–4, there were 14 males (7.78 percent) and 30 females (16.67 percent). Within the group score range of 5–6, there were 30 males (16.67 percent) and 28 females (15.56 percent). In the final group, the distribution of males and females was 28 males (15.56 percent) and 50 females (27.78 percent). Table III displays, for both males and females, a distribution of patients based on the scoring pattern that they received.

Table III: Distribution of patients according to gender and Alvarado Score

Score	Gender	Acute Appendicitis	Non-AA	Total	P-Value
1-4	Male	1 (7.1%)	13 (92.9%)	14 (100%)	0.318
	Female	0	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	
5-6	Male	1 (3.3%)	29 (96.6%)	30 (100%)	0.082
	Female	5 (17.8%)	23 (82.2%)	28 (100%)	
7-10	Male	27 (96.5%)	1 (3.5%)	28 (100%)	0.709
	Female	48 (96%)	2 (4%)	50 (100%)	
Total	Male	29 (40%)	43 (60%)	72 (100%)	0.157
	Female	53 (49%)	55 (51%)	108 (100%)	

There was no significant difference between Alvarado score (AS) and acute appendicitis (AA)diagnosis according to the patient's age as shown in table IV.

The value of 6 was chosen as the cutoff for appendicectomy. The further examination of the data revealed that all 78 patients, including 28 males and 50 females, who were classified as having a score in the range of 7 had their appendices removed surgically. After performing a histopathological analysis on the specimens, it was determined that 75 of the patients had acute appendicitis. Reassessment revealed that 17 (9.44 percent) of the 58 patients with a score between 5

and 6 underwent appendectomy within 36 hours of admission. There were 5 males and 12 females included in this group. It was discovered that patients who had delayed appendectomy procedures did so either because the severity of their symptoms had worsened and their clinical condition had deteriorated or because, after a recalculation of the scoring system, they were classified as having a score of seven or lower. In this group, there were 11 patients (four males and seven females) for whom the appendix that was removed showed normal histology, while in 6 patients (35.29 percent), the appendix was acutely inflamed. 44 patients in the first group who had scores in the range of 1–4 were released from the hospital within the first 24 hours of their admission. Within the first twenty-four hours after their discharge, five patients from this group were readmitted with complaints of worsening symptoms and underwent appendectomy as a result of their conditions. Upon readmission with a complaint of ongoing pain in the right iliac fossa, it was discovered that they had a score that was greater than or equal to 6. Histopathology performed after surgery determined that the patient in question had acute appendicitis.

Appendicitis was confirmed in 29 males and 53 females, giving a negative appendectomy rate of 17.14 percent in males and 18.46 percent in females, with a negative appendectomy rate of 18 percent overall. The data collected were analyzed statistically, and it was found that there were 35 males and 65 females who underwent appendectomy. Appendicitis was confirmed in 82 out of 100 patients who underwent appendectomy, according to the findings in the operative notes and the histology reports (82 percent). When it came to males, the values for sensitivity and specificity were 93.13 percent and 83.33 percent, respectively, while the values for positive and negative predictive values were 96.4 percent and 71.42 percent, respectively. It was found that females had a sensitivity of 90.56 percent, a specificity of 83.33 percent, a positive predictive value of 96 percent, and a negative predictive value of 66.66 percent. Overall, the Alvarado score had a positive predictive value of 96.15 percent, a negative predictive value of 68.18 percent, as well as a sensitivity of 91.46 percent and a specificity of 83.33 percent respectively. When it came to predicting acute appendicitis, the diagnostic accuracy was at a rate of 90%. As can be seen in table IV, there was no discernible difference in the diagnosis of AS or AA based on the gender of the patient.

Table IV: Distribution of patients according to gender and Alvarado Score

Score	Gender	Acute Appendicitis	Non-AA	Total	P-Value
1-4	Male	1 (7.1%)	13 (92.9%)	14 (100%)	0.318
	Female	0	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	
5-6	Male	1 (3.3%)	29 (96.6%)	30 (100%)	0.082
	Female	5 (17.8%)	23 (82.2%)	28 (100%)	
7-10	Male	27 (96.5%)	1 (3.5%)	28 (100%)	0.709
	Female	48 (96%)	2 (4%)	50 (100%)	
Total	Male	29 (40%)	43 (60%)	72 (100%)	0.157
	Female	53 (49%)	55 (51%)	108 (100%)	

Table V: Distribution of patients according to BMI and alvarado score

Score	BMI	Acute Appendicitis	Non-AA	Total	P Value
1-4	≤25	0 (0%)	29 (100%)	29 (100%)	0.341
	>25	1 (6.6%)	14 (93.4%)	15 (100%)	
5-6	≤25	4 (10.3%)	35 (89.7%)	39 (100%)	1
	>25	2 (10.5%)	17 (93.4%)	19 (100%)	
	≤25	66 (95.6%)	3 (4.4%)	69 (100%)	1

7-10	>25	9 (100%)	0 (0%)	9 (100%)	0.009
Total	≤25	70 (51%)	67 (49.9%)	137 (100%)	
	>25	12 (29.9%)	31 (72.1%)	43 (100%)	

Table VI: Distribution of patients according to age and Alvarado score

Score	Age group	Acute Appendicitis	Non-AA	Total	P Value
1-4	≤30	1 (3.1%)	31 (96.9%)	32 (100%)	1
	>30	0 (0%)	12 (100%)	12 (100%)	
5-6	≤30	4 (10.5%)	34 (89.5%)	38 (100%)	1
	>30	2 (10%)	18 (90%)	20 (100%)	
7-10	≤30	58 (98.3%)	1 (1.7%)	59 (100%)	0.430
	>30	18 (94.7%)	1 (5.3%)	19 (100%)	
Total	≤30	63 (48.9%)	66 (51.1%)	129 (100%)	0.252
	>30	20 (39.2%)	31 (60.8%)	51 (100%)	

Table VII: Distribution of patients according to symptoms duration and Alvarado score

Score	Symptoms	Acute Appendicitis	Non-AA	Total	P Value
1-4	≤24 hours	1 (4.1%)	23 (95.9%)	24 (100%)	1
	>24 hours	0 (0%)	20 (100%)	20 (100%)	
5-6	≤24 hours	2 (7.7%)	24 (92.3%)	26 (100%)	0.68
	>24 hours	4 (12.5%)	28 (87.5%)	32 (100%)	
7-10	≤24 hours	29 (96.6%)	1 (3.33%)	30 (100%)	1
	>24 hours	46 (95.8%)	2 (4.2%)	48 (100%)	
Total	≤24 hours	32 (40%)	48 (60%)	80 (100%)	0.228
	>24 hours	50 (50%)	50 (50%)	100 (100%)	

Discussion

The most common cause of acute abdominal pain across all age ranges is acute appendicitis, also known as AA. It is still difficult to make an accurate and timely diagnosis in patients who have been admitted to the emergency room with a provisional diagnosis of alcoholism (17). According to the findings of epidemiological studies, appendicitis is most prevalent in individuals between the ages of 10 and 20. In line with the findings of (18) Limpawattanasiri C et al., our research found that the incidence was highest in people younger than 20 years old. In our research, we found that females were more frequently affected than males, and other studies (2,19) have found findings that are comparable to ours. Even for the most seasoned medical professional, it is possible to feel inadequate when making a diagnosis of acute appendicitis because it continues to be one of the most contentious tasks in general surgery. It's possible that this is because of the disease's varying symptoms as well as the absence of a trustworthy diagnostic test (20). The Alvarado scoring system is an easy-to-use and low-cost decision making tool that helps surgeons clinically diagnose a case of suspected acute appendicitis in a patient with 21.

According to the findings of these studies, patients with an AS score of 4 or lower should be discharged from the hospital. When patients with AS 4 were separated into two groups, those who were discharged after monitoring (emergency

room and surgery clinic) and those who underwent surgery, 17 of the 100 patients who participated in the study were in the first group and were discharged. This was done in the study by Khan et al. Within forty-eight hours, three of the patients had returned, and the new AS was determined to be seven. They went through with the operation, and AA was found in (17 percent).

22 Winn et al. discharged 12 patients (9.8 percent) and did not provide any medical follow-up; four patients were readmitted, and two underwent surgery; however, appendicitis was not found in either patient. In the current study, there were a total of 44 patients who were discharged with an AS score of 4 or lower. Of those 44 patients, 5 required surgery due to re-admission, and one patient was found to have AA (20 percent).

Patients with an AS score of 4 or lower should be monitored, and patients who are discharged from the hospital should be informed about abdominal pain and asked to return to the facility if their pain worsens. Patients with an AS of less than four should be hospitalized and monitored, and their AS should be calculated on a regular basis. This is especially important in the case of patients traveling from a significant distance. Regarding the patients who were diagnosed with AS 5-6, 17 patients ultimately decided to have surgery after being observed. Acute appendicitis was diagnosed in 6 patients, which is 35.30% of the total, and these patients all went on to undergo surgery after being observed. The rate of negative appendectomy was 64.70%. This is in accordance with the findings of Shah et al., who reported a negative appendectomy rate of 71.4 percent in Groups (A alvarado ≥ 6 as opposed to 11.1 percent in Group B alvarado ≥ 7). When it came to the patients who had AS 7-10, AA was found in 96% (7/5) of them, and the rate of patients who had a negative appendectomy was 4%. According to Shah et al., who reported 11.1 percent negative appendectomy rates in Groups B alvarado ≥ 7 , this finding is consistent with their findings. The results were in line with what was found in the literature (24,27). According to the findings of our research, the negative appendectomy rate was found to be 80 percent for AS less than 4, 64.71 percent for AS 5-6, and 4 percent for AS 7-10, respectively. This indicates that for high Alvarado scores, the likelihood of having false positive cases is reduced; consequently, there is a requirement for additional evaluation and (24) observation in the group that has a score of less than six. When the data was cross-referenced, there were 75 cases that were a true positive, 3 cases that were a false positive, 7 cases that were a false negative, and 15 cases that were a true negative. When using histopathology as the gold standard, it produced a sensitivity of 91.46 percent, a specificity of 83.33 percent, a positive predictive value of 96.15 percent, a negative predictive value of 68.18 percent, and a diagnostic accuracy of 90 percent for the Alvarado score in predicting acute appendicitis. Our findings are consistent with those that were obtained by Kanumba et al. in 2011. They found that the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive, and negative predictive values, as well as the accuracy of the Alvarado score, were 94.1 percent, 90.4 percent, 95.2 percent, and 88.4 percent, respectively. The findings of the current study are comparable with those of a number of other studies, with the exception of those conducted by Jalil et al. in 2011 (SN = 66 percent, SP = 81 percent) (26) and Memon et al. in 2009 (SN = 58.2 percent, SP = 88.9 percent), both of which found a significantly lower sensitivity and specificity for the Alvarado Score.

This variation might be due to the fact that different surgeons have different levels of skill in accurately performing and interpreting the Alvarado score. Our observation agrees with those of Jalil et al in 2011 ((97 percent vs. 92 percent)(26), 28 Talukder et al, in 2009 (93 percent vs. 84 percent), and 25 Kanumba et al, in 2011 (95.8 percent vs. 88.3 percent),(25), who also observed a similar difference in the sensitivity of the Alvarado score between male and female patients. When stratified, the sensitivity

In the current study, the effectiveness of AS (4, 5-6,7-10) was evaluated according to age, gender, and body mass index. In terms of the AS's reliability, the current study discovered no significant gender differences, age differences, or BMI differences between the participants.

Conclusion

According to the findings of this study, the Alvarado score accurately predicts appendicitis and performs very well when applied to men. The Alvarado score functions very well as a criterion for "ruling out" candidates in the context of decision rules for observation or admission (high sensitivity). The Alvarado score cannot be used as a decision rule in relation to surgery, and therefore it cannot be used to "rule in" a diagnosis of appendicitis without first undergoing surgical assessment and additional diagnostic testing. The Alvarado score could be used as a triage decision rule, which would be beneficial for patients who present themselves in primary care settings as well as emergency departments, particularly in nations with limited healthcare resources.

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